

Strong Convergent Iterative Techniques for 2-generalized Hybrid Mappings and Split Equilibrium Problems

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Abstract. In this paper, we suggest a new iterative scheme for finding a common element of the set of solutions of a split equilibrium problem and the set of fixed points of 2-generalized hybrid mappings in Hilbert spaces. We show that the iteration converges strongly to a common solution of the considered problems. A numerical example is illustrated to verify the validity of the proposed algorithm. The results obtained in this paper extend and improve some known results in the literature.

1. Introduction

Let H_1 and H_2 be real Hilbert spaces with the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ and the norm $\| \cdot \|$. $F_1: C_1 \times C_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $F_2: C_2 \times C_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are two equilibrium functions, where C_1 and C_2 are nonempty closed convex subsets of H_1 and H_2 , respectively. If $A: H_1 \rightarrow H_2$ is a bounded linear operator, then split equilibrium problem (SEP) is defined as follows:

Find $x^* \in C_1$ such that

$$F_1(x^*, x) \geq 0 \quad \forall x \in C_1, \tag{1}$$

and $y^* = Ax^* \in C_2$ such that

$$F_2(y^*, y) \geq 0 \quad \forall y \in C_2. \tag{2}$$

The set of all solutions of this split equilibrium problem is denoted by Ω , i.e,

$$\Omega = \{z \in C : z \in EP(F_1) \text{ such that } Az \in EP(F_2)\},$$

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where $EP(F_1)$ and $EP(F_2)$ denote the sets of all solutions of the equilibrium problems (1) and (2), respectively.

Equilibrium problem has received much attention due to its applications in a large variety of problems arising in physics, optimizations, economics and some others. The split equilibrium problem (1)-(2) constitute a pair of equilibrium problems where is the generalization of split feasibility problems. Some iterative methods have been rapidly established for solving these problems (see [1–10]).

Let H be a real Hilbert space and C be a nonempty closed convex subset of H . A mapping $T : C \rightarrow C$ is said to be:

(1) *nonexpansive* if $\|T(x) - T(y)\| \leq \|x - y\|, \forall x, y \in C$;

(2) *quasi-nonexpansive* if $\|T(x) - p\| \leq \|x - p\|$ for all $x \in C$ and $p \in F(T)$, where $F(T)$ denotes the set of fixed points of T ;

(3) *nonspreading* if

$$2\|T(x) - T(y)\|^2 \leq \|T(x) - y\|^2 + \|T(y) - x\|^2, \forall x, y \in C;$$

(4) *firmly nonexpansive* if

$$\|Tx - Ty\|^2 \leq \langle Tx - Ty, x - y \rangle, \forall x, y \in C;$$

It is obvious that the above inequality is equivalent to

$$\|Tx - Ty\|^2 \leq \|x - y\|^2 - \|(I - T)x - (I - T)y\|^2, \forall x, y \in C; \tag{3}$$

(5) α -*inverse strongly monotone* if there exists $\alpha > 0$ such that

$$\langle x - y, Tx - Ty \rangle \geq \alpha \|Tx - Ty\|^2, \forall x, y \in C;$$

(6) *hybrid* if

$$3\|T(x) - T(y)\|^2 \leq \|x - y\|^2 + \|Tx - y\|^2 + \|Ty - x\|^2, \forall x, y \in C;$$

(7) (α, β) -*generalized hybrid* if there exist $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\alpha \|T(x) - T(y)\|^2 + (1 - \alpha) \|x - Ty\|^2 \leq \beta \|Tx - y\|^2 + (1 - \beta) \|x - y\|^2, \forall x, y \in C;$$

(8) 2 -*generalized hybrid mapping* if there exist $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ such that for all $x, y \in C$

$$\alpha_1 \|T^2x - Ty\|^2 + \alpha_2 \|Tx - Ty\|^2 + (1 - \alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \|x - Ty\|^2 \leq \beta_1 \|T^2x - y\|^2 + \beta_2 \|Tx - y\|^2 + (1 - \beta_1 - \beta_2) \|x - y\|^2,$$

such a mapping is called a $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2)$ -generalized hybrid mapping.

It is also easy to see that

a $(1, 0)$ -generalized hybrid mapping is nonexpansive.

a $(2, 1)$ -generalized hybrid mapping is nonspreading.

a $(3/2, 1/2)$ -generalized hybrid mapping is hybrid.

a $(0, \alpha_2, 0, \beta_2)$ -generalized hybrid mapping is (α_2, β_2) -generalized hybrid.

a 2 -generalized hybrid mapping is quasi-nonexpansive.

In [11], Hojo et al. give two examples of 2 -generalized hybrid mappings which are not generalized hybrid mapping.

Recently, the existence of fixed points and the convergence theorems of hybrid mappings have been studied by many authors (see [12–20]).

Very recently, Alizadeh and Moradlou [21–23] have obtained some weak convergence theorems for 2 -generalized hybrid mapping and equilibrium problems.

Motivated by the above works, in this paper we introduce and consider a new iterative algorithm for a common element of the sets of solutions of the split equilibrium problems and common fixed points of 2 -generalized hybrid mapping in Hilbert spaces. Under suitable conditions, some strong convergence for the sequences generated by the algorithm to a common solution of the problems is proved. The results presented in the paper extend and improve the corresponding results announced by Alizadeh and Moradlou [21], and some others.

2. Preliminaries and lemmas

In this section, we give some definitions and preliminaries which will be used in the sequel.

Let H be a real Hilbert space and C be a nonempty closed convex subset of H . The operator P_C denotes the Metric projection from H onto C . It is a fact that P_C is a firmly nonexpansive mapping from H onto C . Further, for any $x \in H, z = P_C x$ if and only if $\langle x - z, z - y \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C$.

Lemma 2.1 ([24]). Let H be a real Hilbert space and $T: H \rightarrow H$ be a nonexpansive mapping. Then for all $(x, y) \in H \times F(T)$, we have

$$\langle x - T(x), y - T(x) \rangle \leq \frac{1}{2} \|x - T(x)\|^2.$$

Lemma 2.2 (Demiclosedness principle). Let T be a nonexpansive mapping on a closed convex subset C of a real Hilbert space H . Then $I - T$ is demiclosed at any point $y \in H$, that is, if $x_n \rightarrow x$ and $x_n - Tx_n \rightarrow y \in H$, then $x - Tx = y$.

To obtain our main results, we need the following assumptions.

Assumption 2.3 ([25, 26]). Let $F: C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an equilibrium function satisfying the following assumptions:

- (1) $F(x, x) = 0, \forall x \in C$;
- (2) F is monotone, i.e., $F(x, y) + F(y, x) \leq 0, \forall x, y \in C$;
- (3) F is hemicontinuous with respect to the first variable, i.e., for each $x, y, z \in C, \limsup_{t \rightarrow 0^+} F(tz + (1-t)x, y) \leq F(x, y)$;
- (4) for each $x \in C$, the function $y \mapsto F(x, y)$ is convex and lower semi-continuous.

Lemma 2.4 ([27]). Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert space H and $F: C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an equilibrium function which satisfies the Assumption 2.3. Then for all $r > 0$, the resolvent of the equilibrium function $T_r^F: H \rightarrow C$ defined by

$$T_r^F(x) = \{z \in C : F(z, y) + \frac{1}{r} \langle y - z, z - x \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C\}, \forall x \in H,$$

is well defined and satisfies the following conditions:

- (1) $T_r^F(x)$ is nonempty and single-valued for each $x \in H$;
- (2) T_r^F is firmly nonexpansive, i.e. for any $x, y \in H$,

$$\|T_r^F(x) - T_r^F(y)\|^2 \leq \langle T_r^F(x) - T_r^F(y), x - y \rangle;$$

- (3) $F(T_r^F) = EP(F)$;
- (4) the set $EP(F)$ is closed and convex;
- (5) for $r, s > 0$ and for all $x, y \in H$, one has

$$\|T_r^F(x) - T_s^F(y)\|^2 \leq \|x - y\| + |1 - \frac{s}{r}| \|T_r^F(x) - x\|.$$

Lemma 2.5 ([28]). Let H be a real Hilbert space. For all $x, y \in H$,

$$\|\alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y\|^2 = \alpha \|x\|^2 + (1 - \alpha) \|y\|^2 - \alpha(1 - \alpha) \|x - y\|^2, \forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Now, we give a new iterative scheme as follows:

Let C_1 be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert space H_1 and $S: C_1 \rightarrow C_1$ is a 2-generalized hybrid mapping.

For an initial point $x_0 \in C_1$, let $x_1 = P_{C_1} x_0$ and $D_1 = C_1$. Then

$$\begin{cases} u_n = T_{r_n}^{F_1} [I - \gamma A^* (I - T_{r_n}^{F_2}) A] x_n, \\ v_n = (1 - \beta_n) u_n + \frac{\beta_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n \\ y_n = (1 - \alpha_n) u_n + \frac{\alpha_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n \\ D_{n+1} = \{x \in D_n : \|y_n - x\| \leq \|x_n - x\|\}, \\ x_{n+1} = P_{D_{n+1}} x_0, \forall n \geq 1. \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

For this iterative scheme, we will discuss its strong convergence and also prove that its limit point belongs to $F(S) \cap \Omega$, where $F(S)$ is a set of fixed points of S .

3. The main results

In this section, we show some strong convergence theorems for finding a common element of the solution set of split equilibrium problems and the set of fixed points of 2-generalized hybrid mapping in a Hilbert space.

Throughout this section we need the following assumptions:

(A1) $C_1 \subset H_1$ and $C_2 \subset H_2$ are nonempty closed convex subsets of the real Hilbert spaces H_1 and H_2 , respectively.

(A2) $A : H_1 \rightarrow H_2$ is a bounded linear mapping.

(A3) $S : C_1 \rightarrow C_1$ is a 2-generalized hybrid mapping.

(A4) $F_1 : C_1 \times C_1 \rightarrow R, F_2 : C_2 \times C_2 \rightarrow R$ are two equilibrium functions such that Assumption 2.3 holds.

(A5) $T_{r_n}^{F_1} : H_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_{r_n}^{F_2} : H_2 \rightarrow C_2$ are the resolvent of the equilibrium functions F_1 and F_2 , respectively.

We also need the following lemma.

Lemma 3.1 ([26]). Assume that the assumptions (A1–A5) are satisfied and $r_n \in (r, +\infty)$ with $r > 0, \gamma \in (0, \frac{1}{L})$, where L is the spectral radius of A^*A . Then $A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A$ is a $\frac{1}{L}$ -inverse strongly monotone mapping and $I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A$ is a nonexpansive mapping.

Theorem 3.2. Assume that the assumptions (A1 – A5) are satisfied and $0 < \alpha < \alpha_n, \beta_n < \beta < 1, r < r_n < \infty$, for $\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1), r > 0, \gamma \in (0, \frac{1}{L})$, where L is the spectral radius of A^*A . In addition, if $\Theta = F(S) \cap \Omega \neq \emptyset$, then for any $x_0 \in C_1$, the sequence $\{x_n\}$ defined by (4) converges strongly to some point $p \in \Theta$.

Proof. We shall divide the proof into five steps.

Step (I): $\Theta \subset D_n, \forall n \geq 1$.

Obviously, $\Theta \subset D_1 = C_1$. By induction, assume that $\Theta \subset D_n$ for some $n \geq 1$. We only need to show that $\Theta \subset D_{n+1}$. For any $p \in \Theta$, we have $p = T_{r_n}^{F_1}p$ and $(I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A)p = p$ from Lemma 2.4. The Lemma 3.1 results in

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_n - p\| &= \|T_{r_n}^{F_1}(I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A)x_n - T_{r_n}^{F_1}(I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A)p\| \\ &\leq \|(I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A)x_n - (I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A)p\| \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Since $p \in F(S)$ and S is quasi-nonexpansive, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|Sv_n - p\| &\leq \|v_n - p\| \\ &= \|(1 - \beta_n)u_n + \frac{\beta_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n - p\| \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - p\| + \frac{\beta_n}{n} \|\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (S^k u_n - p)\| \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - p\| + \frac{\beta_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \|(S^k u_n - p)\| \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - p\| + \frac{\beta_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \|(Su_n - p)\| \\ &\leq \|u_n - p\|. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Combining (4), (5), (6) and Lemma 2.5, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|y_n - p\|^2 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)u_n + \frac{\alpha_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n - p\|^2 \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)(u_n - p) + \alpha_n \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n - p\right)\|^2 \\
 &= (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (S^k v_n - p) \right\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) \left\| u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n \right\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \|S^k v_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) \left\| u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n \right\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n \|v_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) \left\| u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n \right\|^2 \\
 &\leq \|u_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) \left\| u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n \right\|^2 \\
 &\leq \|u_n - p\|^2 \\
 &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

which implies that $p \in D_{n+1}$. Therefore, $\Theta \subset D_{n+1}$.

Step (II): The sequence $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

According to (4) and the Step (I), it is obvious that D_n is nonempty closed and convex subset of C_1 . Since $\Theta \subset D_{n+1} \subset D_n$, for all $n \geq 1$, we obtain from $x_{n+1} = P_{D_{n+1}}x_0$ that

$$\|x_{n+1} - x_0\| = \|P_{D_{n+1}}x_0 - x_0\| \leq \|p - x_0\|, \forall p \in \Theta,$$

which implies that $\{x_n\}$ is bounded. By $x_n = P_{D_n}x_0$, we have

$$\langle x_0 - x_n, x_n - x_{n+1} \rangle \geq 0.$$

Therefore,

$$0 \leq \langle x_0 - x_n, x_n - x_{n+1} \rangle \leq -\|x_n - x_0\|^2 + \|x_{n+1} - x_0\| \|x_0 - x_n\|.$$

Hence,

$$\|x_n - x_0\| \leq \|x_{n+1} - x_0\|, \quad \forall n \geq 1,$$

which implies that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x_0\|$ exists. For any $n > m \geq 1$, $x_m = P_{D_m}x_0$, we also have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_n - x_0\|^2 &= \|x_n - x_m + x_m - x_0\|^2 \\
 &= \|x_n - x_m\|^2 + \|x_m - x_0\|^2 + 2\langle x_n - x_m, x_m - x_0 \rangle \\
 &\geq \|x_n - x_m\|^2 + \|x_m - x_0\|^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we get

$$\|x_n - x_m\|^2 \leq \|x_n - x_0\|^2 - \|x_m - x_0\|^2 \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n, m \rightarrow \infty. \tag{8}$$

Hence $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. We may assume that

$$x_n \rightarrow x^*, \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{9}$$

Step (III): $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\| = 0$.

Since $x_{n+1} \in D_{n+1} \subset D_n$, by the definition of D_{n+1} , we have

$$\|y_n - x_{n+1}\| \leq \|x_n - x_{n+1}\|.$$

It follows from (8) that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|y_n - x_{n+1}\| = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x_{n+1}\| = 0. \tag{10}$$

Therefore, we obtain from (8) and (10)

$$\|y_n - x_n\| \leq \|y_n - x_{n+1}\| + \|x_{n+1} - x_n\| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{11}$$

Further, from (7), we have

$$\|y_n - p\|^2 \leq \|u_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n\|^2. \tag{12}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n\|^2 &\leq \|u_n - p\|^2 - \|y_n - p\|^2, \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 - \|y_n - p\|^2, \\ &\leq \|x_n - y_n\|(\|x_n - p\| + \|y_n - p\|). \end{aligned}$$

By $0 < \alpha < \alpha_n < \beta < 1$ and (11), we have

$$\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n\| \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{13}$$

Furthermore, $p \in \Theta$ ensures $p = T_{r_n}^{F_1} p$ and $p = (I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A)p$. Therefore, we have from Lemma 3.1 and (3)

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_n - p\|^2 &= \|T_{r_n}^{F_1}[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - T_{r_n}^{F_1}[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]p\|^2 \\ &\leq \|[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - [I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]p\|^2 \\ &\quad - \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - (I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]p\|^2 \\ &= \|x_n - p\|^2 - 2\gamma \langle x_n - p, A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n - A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ap \rangle \\ &\quad + \gamma^2 \|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n - A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ap\|^2 \\ &\quad - \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - (I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]p\|^2 \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 + \gamma(\gamma - \frac{2}{L})\|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2 - \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n\|^2. \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

From (12) and (14), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma(\frac{2}{L} - \gamma)\|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2 &+ \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n\|^2 \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 - \|u_n - p\|^2 \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 - \|y_n - p\|^2 \\ &\leq \|x_n - y_n\|(\|x_n - p\| + \|y_n - p\|). \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Since $\gamma \in (0, \frac{1}{L})$, using (11), we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\| = 0, \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n\| = 0. \tag{16}$$

Since $T_{r_n}^{F_1}$ is firmly nonexpansive, so we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_n - p\|^2 &= \|T_{r_n}^{F_1}[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - T_{r_n}^{F_1}p\|^2 \\ &\leq \| [I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - p \|^2 \\ &= \|x_n - p\|^2 + \gamma^2 \|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2 + 2\gamma \langle p - x_n, A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n \rangle \\ &= \|x_n - p\|^2 + \gamma^2 \|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2 + 2\gamma \langle Ap - Ax_n, (I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma^2 \|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2 &= \gamma^2 \langle (I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n, AA^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n \rangle \\ &\leq L\gamma^2 \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

We also have from Lemma 2.1

$$\begin{aligned} 2\gamma \langle Ap - Ax_n, (I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n \rangle &= 2\gamma \langle Ap - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n - (Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n), (I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n \rangle \\ &= 2\gamma \{ \langle Ap - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n, Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n \rangle - \|Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n\|^2 \} \\ &\leq 2\gamma \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \|Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n\|^2 - \|Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n\|^2 \right\} \\ &= -\gamma \|Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_n - p\|^2 &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 + L\gamma^2 \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2 - \gamma \|Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n\|^2 \\ &= \|x_n - p\|^2 + \gamma(L\gamma - 1) \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2, \end{aligned}$$

which implies from (12) that

$$\begin{aligned} -\gamma(L\gamma - 1) \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\|^2 &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 - \|u_n - p\|^2 \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 - \|y_n - p\|^2 \\ &\leq \|x_n - y_n\|(\|x_n - p\| + \|y_n - p\|). \end{aligned}$$

Due to $\gamma \in (0, \frac{1}{L})$ and (11), we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\| = 0. \tag{17}$$

Hence, we obtain from (16)

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_n - x_n\| &= \|T_{r_n}^{F_1}[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - x_n\| \\ &\leq \|T_{r_n}^{F_1}[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - [I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n\| + \|[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n - x_n\| \\ &= \|(I - T_{r_n}^{F_1})[I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A]x_n\| + \gamma \|A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\| \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Using (4) and Lemma 2.5, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|v_n - p\|^2 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)u_n + \frac{\beta_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n - p\|^2 \\ &= \|(1 - \beta_n)(u_n - p) + \beta_n \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n - p \right)\|^2 \\ &= (1 - \beta_n) \|u_n - p\|^2 + \beta_n \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (S^k u_n - p) \right\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n) \|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \beta_n \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \|S^k v_n - p\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \beta_n\|u_n - p\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq \|u_n - p\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2.
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

So, we get from (19) and (5)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|y_n - p\|^2 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)u_n + \frac{\alpha_n}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n - p\|^2 \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)(u_n - p) + \alpha_n(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n - p)\|^2 \\
 &= (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n\|\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (S^k v_n - p)\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \|S^k v_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n\|v_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k v_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n\|v_n - p\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|u_n - p\|^2 + \alpha_n[\|u_n - p\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2] \\
 &\leq \|u_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n\beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 - \alpha_n\beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

which implies from (20) and $0 < \alpha < \alpha_n < \beta < 1$ that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha\beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2 &\leq \alpha_n\beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 - \|y_n - p\|^2 \\
 &\leq (\|x_n - p\| + \|y_n - p\|)(\|x_n - y_n\|).
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

In virtue of $0 < \alpha < \beta_n < \beta < 1$, (9), (11) and (21), we get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|u_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n\| = 0. \tag{22}$$

Step (IV): $x^* \in \Theta = F(S) \cap \Omega$, where x^* is the limit in (3.5).

To do so, we firstly show that $x^* \in \Omega$.

By the boundedness of A and (9), we get $Ax_n \rightarrow Ax^*$. Then we have from Lemma 2.4 and (17)

$$\|T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n - T_r^{F_2}Ax_n\| \leq |1 - \frac{r}{r_n}| \|T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n - Ax_n\| \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

and

$$\|T_r^{F_2}Ax_n - Ax_n\| \leq \|T_r^{F_2}Ax_n - T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n\| + \|T_{r_n}^{F_2}Ax_n - Ax_n\| \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Since $T_r^{F_2}$ is nonexpansive, we easily get from Lemma 2.2 and Lemma 2.4

$$T_r^{F_2}Ax^* = Ax^*, \text{ i.e. } Ax^* \in F(T_r^{F_2}) = EP(F_2).$$

Let $w_n = (I - \gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})A)x_n$. By (16) we have

$$\|w_n - x_n\| = \|\gamma A^*(I - T_{r_n}^{F_2})Ax_n\| \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

We also have from (16)

$$\|T_{r_n}^{F_1}w_n - T_r^{F_1}w_n\| \leq |1 - \frac{r}{r_n}| \|T_{r_n}^{F_1}w_n - w_n\| \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Therefore,

$$\|T_r^{F_1}w_n - w_n\| \leq \|T_r^{F_1}w_n - T_{r_n}^{F_1}w_n\| + \|T_{r_n}^{F_1}w_n - w_n\| \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Since $T_r^{F_1}$ is nonexpansive, we get from Lemma 2.2 and Lemma 2.4

$$T_r^{F_1}x^* = x^*, \text{ i.e. } x^* \in F(T_r^{F_1}) = EP(F_1).$$

Therefore, $x^* \in \Omega$.

Now, we prove that $x^* \in F(S)$.

By means of (18) and (22), we easily get from $x_n \rightarrow x^*$

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n \rightarrow x^*, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{23}$$

Since S is a 2-generalized hybrid mapping, there exist $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2 \in R$ such that for all $x, y \in C_1$

$$\alpha_1 \|S^2x - Sy\|^2 + \alpha_2 \|Sx - Sy\|^2 + (1 - \alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \|x - Sy\|^2 \leq \beta_1 \|S^2x - y\|^2 + \beta_2 \|Sx - y\|^2 + (1 - \beta_1 - \beta_2) \|x - y\|^2.$$

Since $F(S) \neq \emptyset$, then S is quasi-nonexpansive. So $\|S^n u_n - p\| \leq \|u_n - p\| \leq \|x_n - p\|$, which implies that $\{S^n u_n\}$ is bounded. Since S is a 2-generalized hybrid mapping, we have for all $y \in C_1$ and $k = 0, 2, 3, \dots, n - 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \beta_1 \|S^{k+2}x_n - y\|^2 + \beta_2 \|S^{k+1}x_n - y\|^2 + (1 - \beta_1 - \beta_2) \|S^k x_n - y\|^2 \\ &\quad - \alpha_1 \|S^{k+2}x_n - Sy\|^2 - \alpha_2 \|S^{k+1}x_n - Sy\|^2 - (1 - \alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \|S^k x_n - Sy\|^2 \\ &= \beta_1 \{ \|S^{k+2}x_n - Sy\|^2 + 2\langle S^{k+2}x_n - Sy, Sy - y \rangle + \|Sy - y\|^2 \} + \beta_2 \{ \|S^{k+1}x_n - Sy\|^2 \\ &\quad + 2\langle S^{k+1}x_n - Sy, Sy - y \rangle + \|Sy - y\|^2 \} + (1 - \beta_1 - \beta_2) \{ \|S^k x_n - Sy\|^2 \\ &\quad + 2\langle S^k x_n - Sy, Sy - y \rangle + \|Sy - y\|^2 \} - \alpha_1 \|S^{k+2}x_n - Sy\|^2 - \alpha_2 \|S^{k+1}x_n - Sy\|^2 \\ &\quad - (1 - \alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \|S^k x_n - Sy\|^2 \\ &= \|Sy - y\|^2 + 2\langle \beta_1 S^{k+2}x_n + \beta_2 S^{k+1}x_n + (1 - \beta_1 - \beta_2) S^k x_n - Sy, Sy - y \rangle \\ &\quad + (\beta_1 - \alpha_1) \{ \|S^{k+2}x_n - Sy\|^2 - \|S^k x_n - Sy\|^2 \} + (\beta_2 - \alpha_2) \{ \|S^{k+1}x_n - Sy\|^2 - \|S^k x_n - Sy\|^2 \} \\ &= \|Sy - y\|^2 + 2\langle S^k x_n - Sy, Sy - y \rangle + 2\langle \beta_1 (S^{k+2}x_n - S^k x_n) + \beta_2 (S^{k+1}x_n - S^k x_n), Sy - y \rangle \\ &\quad + (\beta_1 - \alpha_1) \{ \|S^{k+2}x_n - Sy\|^2 - \|S^k x_n - Sy\|^2 \} + (\beta_2 - \alpha_2) \{ \|S^{k+1}x_n - Sy\|^2 - \|S^k x_n - Sy\|^2 \}. \end{aligned}$$

Summing these inequalities from $k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$ and dividing by n , we have by denoting $z_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S^k u_n$, for all $n \geq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq & \|S y - y\|^2 + 2\langle z_n - S y, S y - y \rangle + 2\frac{1}{n} \langle \beta_1(S^{n+1}x_n - S^n x_n - Sx_n - x_n) + \beta_2(S^n x_n - x_n), S y - y \rangle \\ & + (\beta_1 - \alpha_1)\frac{1}{n} \{ \|S^{n+1}x_n - S y\|^2 + \|S^n x_n - S y\|^2 - \|Sx_n - S y\|^2 - \|x_n - S y\|^2 \} \\ & + (\beta_2 - \alpha_2)\frac{1}{n} \{ \|S^n x_n - S y\|^2 - \|x_n - S y\|^2 \}. \end{aligned}$$

From (23) and the boundedness of $\{S^n u_n\}$, we have

$$0 \leq \|S y - y\|^2 + 2\langle x^* - S y, S y - y \rangle.$$

Denote $y = x^*$, we have

$$0 \leq \|S x^* - x^*\|^2 + 2\langle x^* - S x^*, S x^* - x^* \rangle = -\|S x^* - x^*\|^2.$$

Hence $x^* \in F(S)$. This shows that $x^* \in \Theta$. $\square \quad \square$

4. Numerical Example

In this section, a numerical example will be illustrated to verify the validity of the proposed algorithm in Section 3.

Example 4.1. Consider the following split equilibrium problem driven by 2-generalized hybrid mapping S : find $x \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\begin{cases} F_1(x, \bar{x}) \geq 0, \forall \bar{x} \in C_1, \\ y = Ax \in C_2, \\ F_2(y, \bar{y}) \geq 0, \forall \bar{y} \in C_2, \\ x \in F(S), \end{cases} \tag{24}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= H_2 = \mathbb{R}, \\ C_1 &= [-3, 0], \\ C_2 &= [0, +\infty), \\ F_1(u, v) &= (u - 1)(v - u), \forall u, v \in C_1, \\ F_2(x, y) &= (x + 15)(y - x), \forall x, y \in C_2, \\ Ax &= 3x, \forall x \in \mathbb{R}, \\ Sx &= \frac{1}{3}x, \forall x \in C_1. \end{aligned}$$

By choosing

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_n &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3n}, \\ \beta_n &= \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{6n}, \\ r &= 4, \\ \gamma &= \frac{1}{9}. \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to check that F_1 and F_2 satisfy all conditions in Lemma 3.1, i.e. Assumption 2.3. Analogously to the Theorem 3.2, we abide by the following processes to obtain the solution of (24).

$$\begin{cases} u_n = \frac{1}{25}x_n, \\ v_n = \left(\frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{6n}\right)u_n + \frac{1}{n}\left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{6n}\right)\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{3^k}u_n, \\ y_n = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3n}\right)u_n + \frac{1}{n}\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3n}\right)\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{3^k}v_n. \end{cases}$$

It is easy to get that $0 \in F(0) \cap \Omega$.

Moreover, numerical results in Table 1 for $\{x_n\}$ also is demonstrated as follows

Table 1:

Numerical results for $x_0 = -2$ and $x_0 = -1$			
n	x_n	n	x_n
1	-2.0000	1	1.0000
2	-1.0400	2	-5.2000×10^{-1}
3	-5.3541	3	-2.6770×10^{-1}
4	-2.7456×10^{-1}	4	-1.3728×10^{-1}
5	-1.4054×10^{-1}	5	-7.0270×10^{-2}
6	-7.1863×10^{-2}	6	-3.5932×10^{-2}
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
98	-9.1955×10^{-29}	98	-4.5978×10^{-29}
99	-4.6901×10^{-29}	99	-2.3450×10^{-29}
100	-2.3921×10^{-29}	100	-1.1960×10^{-29}

See table 1 for the values $x_0 = -2$ or $x_0 = -1$, we obtain $x_n \rightarrow 0$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

See Figure 1 and Figure 2 for the values $x_0 = x_1 = -1$ and $x_0 = x_1 = -2$. The computations associated with example were performed using MATLAB software.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 1: A plot of $x_n, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 100$, for Example 4.1

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